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Research Article

**ATTRIBUTES OF SUCCESS AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS
TO PASS THE PROFESSIONAL****Dr. Momina Shahzad Bajwa, Dr. Muhammad Mubeen Bashir, Dr. Noor E Jawairia**
Department of Community Medicine Gujranwala Medical College Gujranwala**Abstract:**

Background: Enrolling into medical school represents the start of a demanding and stressful period for students. Despite a multitude of social, academic, and emotional stressors, most students successfully cope with a complex new life role and achieve academic success. Other students are less able to successfully manage this transition and, sooner or later, decide to withdraw themselves, or face dismissal by medical school.

Material and methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from July to August, 2015 to find out the "Attributes of success among medical students from first year to final year students" visiting GMC, Gujranwala. In this regard a comprehensive questionnaire was prepared to collect the data from respondents. A sample of 88 students was selected by using random sampling.

Results: There were total 88 students, out of which 80 students who passed the annual examination had financial support by their parents and only one student passed without having financial support by their parents. 7 students failed despite availing financial support. In another study I found that there were total 88 students, out of which 65 students who passed their professional showed interest in their studies and 16 students passed who didn't show any interest in their studies. 6 students failed despite showing interest in their studies and only one student out of 7 failed who showed no interest. There were total 88 students, out of which 67 students used social network for their study but only 60 students passed their professional by using social help but all 21 students out of 88, failed who didn't use social network for their study. There were total 88 students, out of which 65 students who passed their professional showed interest in their studies and 16 students passed who didn't show any interest in their studies. 6 students failed despite showing interest in their studies and only one student out of 7 failed who showed no interest. There were total 88 students, out of which 67 students used social network for their study but only 60 students passed their professional by using social help but all 21 students out of 88, failed who didn't use social network for their study.

Conclusion: Medical students showing motivation, planning, work hard showing interest in their studies perform well in their field. Health, sleep and positive approach towards work plays an important role in their success and become a good professional. Active participation in social and cultural activities also play a role in success.

Key Words: Medical students, work hard, interest, luck, motivation, planning, high school grades

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INTRODUCTION:

Pakistan is a low economic country which has a literacy rate of 52 percent out of which females are dominant in education than males and most of the graduate students in medical school are females but unfortunately there are less females that practice in hospitals. This research is about to find out the attributes which play an important role in the success of a graduate student and become a role model for others. Despite a multitude of social, academic, and emotional stressors, most students successfully cope with a complex new life role and achieve academic success.

“Someone with a lot of self-motivation and a driving

Curiosity to understand how nature works.”

“Characteristics of a good graduate student are a

Passion for scholarship, originality and the ability to

Achieve professional goal, not appear in a graduate program to

"Look around" for something interesting, i.e. to go Shopping.[1]

“The prime index of success is motivation.”

It is assumed that an undergraduate has already some Exposure to the discipline prior to coming to a graduate Program.”

“Consistency of effort and self-motivation is key”[2]

Medical students all over the world have different attributes that influence their academic life and are responsible for their success in professional examination. In account of this, we have conducted a research to access those particular attributes that play a vital role in the success of medical students in our institute and help them in becoming successful doctors.

Literature Review:

Surveys for the assessment of attributes for success provide a potentially direct indicator of student performance in the education field and all the means of choosing the best suitable profession. It tells the degree to which an individual regards education as useful, beneficial and effective. Many researches have been done on this topic on local, national and international level.

1) Between October and December 2008 similar study was performed at Kempegowda Institute of Medical Sciences. (KIMS) is a medical college situated in urban Bangalore, India. One hundred and twenty students are admitted to this institution every academic year. This cross-sectional study was conducted between October and December 2008. Current students of the college and interns who had graduated with MBBS from this college were

considered as study participants. Inclusion criteria were that they should have taken at least one university examination and consented to participate in the study. Such willing and eligible students and interns (n = 413) were administered a pretested, self-administered questionnaire to elicit their views on the reasons for their good performance. The questionnaire was pretested on fresh MBBS graduates working as tutors in various departments of KIMS,

Students attributed good performance to being regular in studies (36%), having appropriate study skills (23%), interest in their courses (9%), and support from family and 2 friends (8%).

* 413 students and interns took part in the study out of which 300 students gave response:

119 students were regular in study, 75 had good study skills, 30 had interest in the course, 26 had support from family and friends, 30 do not get easily distracted, 53 had miscellaneous.

2) In another study in 1997, a combined total of 785 students entered medical studies courses in five Flemish universities. Of these, 631 (80.4%) completed the NEO-PI-R (i.e. a measure of the Five-Factor Model of Personality). This was also completed by 914 Year 1 students of seven other academic majors at Ghent University. Year-end scores for medical students were obtained for 607 students in Year 1, for 413 in Year 2, and for 341 in Year 3.

Medical studies falls into the group of major where students score highest on extraversion and agreeableness. Conscientiousness (i.e. self-achievement and self-discipline) significantly predicts final scores in each pre-clinical year. Medical students who score low on conscientiousness and high on gregariousness and excitement-seeking are significantly less likely to sit examinations successfully.

Conclusions: The higher scores for extraversion and agreeableness, two dimensions defining the interpersonal dynamic, may be beneficial for doctors' collaboration and communication skills in future professional practice. Because conscientiousness affects examination results and can be reliably assessed at the start of a medical study career, personality assessment may be a useful tool in student counselling and guidance.

3) During analyzed 30 years in a cross sectional study of students at Nottingham University Medical School, 1126 students graduated, 395 men and 731 women, with a combined graduation GPA of 3.67 and average study duration 7.6 years (range: 5–25 years). Graduation GPA was correlated with high school GPA ($r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$) and EES ($r = 0.34$,

$p < 0.01$). Length of studying was negatively correlated with graduation GPA ($r = -0.39$, $p < 0.01$) and admission test scores ($r = -0.38$, $p < 0.01$).

Linear regression analysis was conducted in order to test whether entrance exam and high school GPA were predictive of academic success. Significant predictors of success defined with medical school GPA were high school GPA ($b = 0.19$, $p < 0.01$) and entrance exam score ($b = 0.29$, $p < 0.01$). This model in total explained 27% of variance.

1) To find attributes of success among medical students so that we can help the students who have low grades to achieve good grades and become professional doctors.

2) To identify potential predictors of success during medical training distinguishing such students from others.

METHODOLOGY:

STUDY DESIGN: Descriptive Cross Sectional.

STUDY SETTING: GMC, Gujranwala
DURATION OF STUDY: 15TH July 2015- 15th Aug 2015.
SAMPLE SIZE: 88 medical students from 1st year to final year M.B.B.S
SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Convenient sampling technique.

- **DATA COLLECTION:** Data was collected by a predesigned questionnaire. Students were interviewed and answers were entered into relevant columns of questionnaire by the researcher.

- **Response of respondents:**
- **Questionnaire filled:** Respondent administered.

- **DATA ANALYSIS:** SPSS Version 13

RESULTS:				
Score in last professional * library use Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Library use		Total
		yes	No	
Score in last professional	pass in annual	38	43	81
	fail in annual	4	3	7
Total		42	46	88

38 students who use the library passed the annual examination and 4 students failed in annual despite using library. 43 students who passed in annual didn't use the library and 3 students who failed the annual exam didn't use library.

Score in last professional* financial support by parents Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Financial support by parents		Total
		yes	no	
Score in last professional	pass in annual	80	1	81
	fail in annual	7	0	7
Total		87	1	88

There were total 88 students, out of which 80 students who passed the annual examination had financial support by their parents and only one student passed without having financial support by their parents. 7 students failed despite availing financial support.

Score in last professional * interest Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Interest		Total
		Yes	No	
Score in last professional	pass in annual	65	16	81
	fail in annual	6	1	7
Total		71	17	88

There were total 88 students, out of which 65 students who passed their professional showed interest in their studies and 16 students passed who didn't show any interest in their studies. 6 students failed despite showing interest in their studies and only one student out of 7 failed who showed no interest.

Score in last professional * use of social network for study Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Use of social network for study		Total
		Yes	No	
Score in last professional	pass in annual	60	21	81
	fail in annual	7	0	7
Total		67	21	88

There were total 88 students, out of which 67 students used social network for their study but only 60 students passed their professional by using social help but all 21 students out of 88, failed who didn't use social network for their study.

Score in last professional * learning style Cross tabulation						
Count						
		Learning style				Total
		Oral	Written	visual	multiple options	
Score in last professional	pass in annual	45	9	18	9	81
	fail in annual	2	1	4	0	7
Total		47	10	22	9	88

There were total 88 students, out of which 45 students were those who chose oral learning style in studies and passed .9 were those who chose written learning style and passed their professional 18 were chose visual leaning style and passed the professional and 9 students chose multiple learning styles for their study and passed their last professional.

Out of 88, only 7 students failed out which 2 used oral learning style, 1 chose written, and 4 chose visual learning style.

Gender * interest Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Interest		Total
		Yes	no	
Gender	male	8	2	10
	female	63	15	78
Total		71	17	88

There were total 88 students, out of which 10 students were male and only 8 males showed interest in their studies and 2 didn't show any interest in their studies .63 students were female who showed interest in their studies, 15 females didn't show any interest.

Education status * library use Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Library use		Total
		yes	no	
Edu status	Urdu medium + F.Sc	6	4	10
	English medium + F.Sc	36	42	78
Total		42	46	88

Out of 88 only 42 students used the library and passed their professional. 46 students didn't use library for studies and passed the examination.

DISCUSSION:

Medical student stress is a growing concern within Pakistani medical education. Despite a multitude of social, academic, and emotional stressors, most students successfully cope with a complex new life role and achieve academic success.

Many researches have been done on this topic on local, national and international level. In a study at Kempegowda institute of medical sciences, students attributed good performance to being regular in studies (36%), having appropriate study skills (23%), interest in their courses (9%), and support from family and 2 friends (8%)

In another study in 1997, a combined total of 785 students entered medical studies courses in five Flemish universities. Of these, 631 completed the NEO-PI-R (i.e. a measure of the Five-Factor Model of Personality). Conclusions: The higher scores for extraversion and agreeableness, two dimensions defining the interpersonal dynamic, may be beneficial for doctors' collaboration and communication skills in future professional practice. Because conscientiousness affects examination results and can be reliably assessed at the start of a medical study career, personality assessment may be a useful tool in student counselling and guidance.

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In my study I found that 38 students who use the library passed the annual examination and 4 students failed in annual despite using library. 43 students who passed in annual didn't use the library and 3 students who failed the annual exam didn't use library.

There were total 88 students, out of which 80 students who passed the annual examination had financial support by their parents and only one student passed without having financial support by their parents. 7 students failed despite availing financial support.

In another study I found that there were total 88 students, out of which 65 students who passed their professional showed interest in their studies and 16 students passed who didn't show any interest in their studies. 6 students failed despite showing interest in their studies and only one student out of 7 failed who showed no interest.

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Out of 88, only 7 students failed out which 2 used oral learning style, 1 chose written, and 4 chose visual learning style.

There were total 88 students, out of which 10 students were male and only 8 males showed interest in their studies and 2 didn't show any interest in their studies .63 students were female who showed interest in their studies, 15 females didn't show any interest.

CONCLUSION:

Hard work, interest, luck, motivation, planning and high school grades are the factors which play a major role in student's success. Many students use more than one learning style i.e. oral, written etc but in my research I found out that students who chose oral learning style performed the best. Use of library also play a significant role in their professional studies. In my study I found that females show a lot of interest

in their studies than males. Social network was also an factor in my study to assess the attributes of success and I found out that students who use social network for their studies perform better in professional studies.

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